

Relative Injective Modules and Relative Flat Modules

Authors : Jianmin Xing, Rufeng Xing

Abstract : Let R be a ring, n a fixed nonnegative integer. The concepts of $(n; 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n; 0)$ -FI-flat modules, and then give some characterizations of these modules over left n -coherent rings are introduced. In addition, we investigate the left and right n -FI-resolutions of R -modules by left (right) derived functors $\text{Ext}_n(-; -)$ ($\text{Tor}_n(-; -)$) over a left n -coherent ring, where n -FI stands for the categories of all $(n; 0)$ -injective left R -modules. These modules together with the left or right derived functors are used to study the $(n; 0)$ -injective dimensions of modules and rings.

Keywords : $(n; 0)$ -injective module, $(n; 0)$ -injective dimension, $(n; 0)$ -FI-injective(flat) module, (Pre)cover, (Pre)envelope

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014